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Why Is *European Science Editing* Not Covered by Dimensions, and Does Dimensions Contain Citation Errors?

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Ansorge¹ compared the citation frequencies of articles published in *European Science Editing* using the Dimensions and Scopus databases and concluded, “Data on citations in the Dimensions database could be more accurate if the references appended to the citing articles listed in the Crossref database were under an open license.” This issue arises when the publishing company neglects to include references when depositing the DOI to Crossref. Evidence of this can be found in Crossref’s participation report (Figure 1A), which shows that no references for *European Science Editing* have been deposited. As a result, citations by *European Science Editing* do not appear in the Dimensions database, which retrieves meta-data information from Crossref. In contrast, *Alpine Entomology*, which is published by the same company as *European Science Editing*, has deposited the majority of its references (88%) to the Crossref metadata (Figure 1B).

A straightforward solution to this deficiency would be to encourage the publishing company of *European Science Editing* to deposit references in Crossref XML files. A more efficient

method for generating Crossref XML files that include references would be to produce full-text Journal Article Tag Suite (JATS) XML files. The conversion of JATS XML to Crossref XML can be easily achieved using a simple script.² The `pmc2crossref.xml` included in the script is also available at <https://github.com/ncbi/P-MCXMLConverters/blob/master/pmc2crossref.xml>. Currently, *European Science Editing* does not produce full-text JATS XML files. However, once established, the production of full-text JATS XML files could serve multiple purposes, including the creation of PDF, PubReader, EPUB 3.0, and DOAJ XML, in addition to facilitating Crossref XML conversion.²

In Table 4 of Ansorge’s article, which presents articles citing *European Science Editing* and indexed in Dimensions but not in Scopus, a footnote was added. The footnote indicated that the source was indexed in Scopus but not the specific article in *Neurointervention* (10.5469/neuroint.2022.00493). However, I conducted a search in Scopus and located the article on August 7, 2023. Therefore, considering the short period between the publication

Figure 1. (A) Crossref participation report for *European Science Editing* [cited September 6, 2023]. Available from: <https://www.crossref.org/members/prep/2258> after inputting journal articles from *European Science Editing*. (B) Crossref participation report for *Alpine Entomology* [cited September 6, 2023]. Available from: <https://www.crossref.org/members/prep/2258> after inputting journal articles from *Alpine Entomology*. Use of Crossref participation reports for 2 journals was permitted by the Crossref.

date (February 1, 2023) and the search date (February 21, 2023), it is possible that this editorial was not yet listed in the Scopus database at the time of the investigation.

Ansorge¹ also stated, “An interesting situation arises for the article with DOI 10.6087/kcse.279, which is listed in the Scopus but not in Dimensions.” The reference of this article of *Science Editing* was initially written as 10.3897/ese.20e53477 but should have read 10.3897/ese.2020.e53477. This error was corrected on September 7, 2023, and reflected in the Crossref metadata. Dimension relies on retrieving Crossref metadata, but the accuracy of the Crossref metadata cannot always be ensured.

In conclusion, Ansorge’s bibliometric study offers a highly intriguing case study focused on a single journal. It confirms the limitations inherent in using Dimensions for bibliometric research. To improve the accuracy and comprehensiveness of the journal network, it is advisable to generate full-text JATS XML

files, submit references to Crossref metadata, and pursue inclusion in the Emerging Sources Citation Index, an additional indexing database alongside Scopus and Dimensions. After the journal is included in the Emerging Sources Citation Index, its citation frequency, including the journal impact factor and citation tracking, is presented so that highly cited topics and their citing researchers can be easily verified. It may enhance collaborations among the researchers in the same field. In addition, the journal’s influence in the communication category can be quantified.

References

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